

CONTRIBUTION OF PUNJAB AND SIND BANK IN THE PROMOTION OF HOCKEY AT JUNIOR LEVEL

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Abstract:

It was in the year 1985 when Punjab and Sind Bank took the first step to promote hockey by forming the senior men's hockey team. In 1994, the Bank decided to promote the National Game at junior level and they inaugurated a junior academy which is running very successfully in Jalandhar and polishing the talent of young hockey players. The aim of present study was to study the contribution of Punjab and Sind Bank in the promotion of hockey at junior level from 1994-2010. Neema (2000) conducted a Case Study titled "Contribution of Shah bad (M) in promotion of Hockey - A Critical Study". Kullar P. (2006) undertook a case study of Sansarpur - Mecca of Indian Hockey. Kaur M. (2009) conducted a study with the title "Contribution of Surjit Singh Hockey Academy at National and International level". The total 25 samples were selected which consisted of the junior level players, coaches and the authorities associated with junior level hockey game. For the present study, self-developed questionnaire and interview schedule were used for collecting data. Observation method was also used for the verification of the data. Investigator also referred to the primary and secondary sources to collect data such as magazines, official records, books and newspapers which carry information about the tournaments, matches and other effective news concerned with the hockey teams of Punjab and Sind Bank. Bank provides stipend, refreshment and education expenses to the players. The players are selected on contract basis for the period of 3 years and they are able to join education on regular basis. Twenty two players were selected. The Bank has contributed a lot towards Hockey at junior level by producing 6 International players who represented Indian team for Junior Hockey World Cup held at Milton Keynes, England in 1998. The junior level players of the bank have also performed extremely well and managed to win the major national level tournaments like All India Sail Champion Colleges Nehru Hockey Tournament, All India Sail Champion Colleges Nehru Hockey Tournament and All India K. D. Babu Memorial Invitational Prize Money Hockey Tournament etc. along with the other Junior National tournaments.

Introduction:

It was in the year 1985 when Punjab and Sind Bank took the first step to promote hockey by forming the senior men's hockey team. In 1994, the Bank decided to promote the National Game at junior level and they inaugurated a junior academy which is running very successfully in Jalandhar and polishing the talent of young hockey players of Punjab. The aim of present study was to study the contribution of Punjab and Sind Bank in the promotion of hockey at junior level from 1994-2010. Neema (2000) conducted a Case Study titled "Contribution of Shah bad (M) in promotion of Hockey - A Critical Study". Kullar P. (2006) undertook a case study of Sansarpur - Mecca of Indian Hockey. Kaur M. (2009) conducted a study with the title "Contribution of Surjit Singh Hockey Academy at National and International level".

Material and Methods:

The total 25 samples were selected consisted of active players, ex-players, coaches, sports authorities and officials of Punjab and Sind Bank. The sample was taken from the junior team of Punjab and Sind Bank. For the present study, self-developed questionnaire and interview schedule were used for collecting data. Observation method was also used for the verification of the data. Investigator also referred to the primary and secondary sources to collect data such as magazines, official records, books and newspapers which carry information about the tournaments, matches and other effective news concerned with the hockey teams of Punjab and Sind Bank.

Results and Discussion:

The management of Punjab and Sind Bank and also the facilities provided by the Bank to the players, then we will discuss on the basis of some basic points. All the three teams are managed by Punjab and Sind Bank. The Bank has recruited so many Olympians, International and National players who manage the different responsibilities of the Hockey Academies and sports sections. Bank has also made a separate sports department which is situated beside the Lyallpur Khalsa College, Jalandhar. Bank has given the Sports Department all the authorities to organize trials, coaching camps for different teams and also to conduct various tournaments. All the office bearers, coaches, physicians and physical trainers are employed and paid by the bank. All the teams practice in the grounds of Lyallpur Khalsa College, Jalandhar. Bank also pays for the Astro-turf of Burlton Park, Jalandhar so that players should have that experience also. Bank has recruited the top International players and Olympians as coaches of the different teams, who put in their whole experience to give best training to the

players. Coaching camps are organized before each competition. Bank has also sponsored the national coaching camps and national hockey championships.

Bank use to conduct All India open trials and a panel of Olympians recommended by the Bank's management selects the players for teams and academies. All the teams are provided with branded playing kits by the bank free of cost. Bank participated in number of National level tournaments and won most of these tournaments. The Punjab and Sind Bank has produced so many excellent players for India and are still doing their job.

Bank provides stipend, refreshment and education expenses to the players. The players are selected on contract basis for the period of 3 years and they are able to join education on regular basis. Twenty two players are selected who are given financial assistance as under:-

- Stipend for First Year - Rs. 1800/month.
- Stipend for Second Year - Rs. 2100/month.
- Stipend for Third Year - Rs. 2500/month

All the junior level players of the Bank's team get the daily allowance for the diet. Each player is given Rs. 120/- for diet on daily basis. Besides that, players are also given refreshment after the training sessions which include juices, milk etc. Bank also provides the Boarding and lodging facility to the junior level players. Bank also provides free education to the junior level hockey players. Bank undertook all their expenses of studies like fee, money for books etc.

Bank has conducted a number of tournaments. No problem is anticipated by the bank in any arena for conducting any tournament. On the other hand, all the teams of Punjab and Sind Bank take part in number of National Tournaments. All the expenses for participation are bear by the Bank on its own. Punjab and Sind Bank sponsor almost all the All India tournaments of Hockey. Bank had also sponsored the Indian team for the Junior World Cup which was held at Milton Keynes in 1998.

This was only due to the hard work of the players and coaches that in the year 1998, 6 players of the bank represented the Indian hockey team in Junior World Cup held at Milton Keynes, England and won the silver medal after 32 years.

The junior level players of the Bank have also performed extremely well in different National level tournaments. The junior academy of the bank has won All India Sail Champion Colleges Nehru Hockey Tournament every time, which held at Rajanandgaon. The junior team of the bank is also a consistent winner of All India Sail Champion Colleges Nehru Hockey Tournament. The junior players of the bank are also very good performers in the Inter-College Hockey Tournaments and have also represented in All India Inter University Competitions number of times. Beside these, junior team of the bank has also won number of other important National Level Tournaments.

Table 1.1: Shows the Achievement of Punjab and Sind Bank Hockey Players at Junior International Level

S.No	Name of the Player	Tournament	Place	Year
1	Baljit Singh Saini (Captain)	Junior World Cup	Milton Keynes, England	1998
2	Teja Singh	Junior World Cup	Milton Keynes, England	1998
3	Baljit Singh Chandi	Junior World Cup	Milton Keynes, England	1998
4	Gurmail Singh	Junior World Cup	Milton Keynes, England	1998
5	Navsher Singh	Junior World Cup	Milton Keynes, England	1998
6	Bikramjit Singh	Junior World Cup	Milton Keynes, England	1998

Table 1.2: Shows the Achievement of Punjab and Sind Bank Hockey Players at Junior National Level

S.No	Tournament	Position	Place	Session
1	Mahant Raja Sarveshardas Memorial All India Hockey Tournament	1 st	Rajanandgaon	2005-2006
2	Boparai All India Hockey Tournament	1 st	Doraha (Ludhiana)	2005-2006
3	Liberals All India Hockey Tournament	2 nd	Nabha	2005-2006
4	Maharaja Sir BP Singh All India Hockey Tournament	2 nd	Balrampur (UP)	2005-2006
5	Sail All India Inter College Hockey Tournament	2 nd	Rourkela	2005-2006
6	All India Jagtar Singh Memorial Hockey Tournament	3 rd	Ludhiana	2005-2006
7	All India Gurbachan Singh Bhasin Hockey Tournament	2 nd	Kartarpur (Jalandhar)	2006-2007
8	All India Sail Champion Colleges Nehru Hockey Tournament	1 st	Delhi	2007-2008
9	All India Liberals Hockey Tournament	4 th	Nabha	2007-2008
10	Inter College Hockey Tournament	1 st	Amritsar	2007-2008
11	Capt. Manjit Singh Gill Memorial Hockey	2 nd	Dhamot Kalan	2007-2008

	Tournament		(Ludhiana)	
12	34 th Junior National Hockey Championship	3 rd	Chennai	2007-2008
13	All India Gold Cup Hockey Tournament	3 rd	Ludhiana	2007-2008
14	Junior Indian Oil Surjit Hockey Tournament	2 nd	Jalandhar	2007-2008
15	All India Sail Champion Colleges Nehru Hockey Tournament	1 st	Gwalior	2009-2010
16	Inter College Hockey Tournament	1 st	Amritsar	2009-2010
17	30 th All India K. D. Babu Memorial Invitational Prize Money Hockey Tournament	3 rd	Lukhnow	2009-2010
18	All India Raja Sarveshverdas Hockey Tournament	1 st	Rajanandgaon	2009-2010
19	All India Inter University	2 nd	Rourkela	2009-2010
20	All India Sir Shadi Lal Rajinder Lal Hockey Tournament	2 nd	Shamli (U. P.)	2009-2010

Conclusion:

The Bank has contributed a lot towards Hockey at junior level by producing 6 International players who represented Indian team for Junior Hockey World Cup held at Milton Keynes, England in 1998. The junior level players of the bank have also performed extremely well and managed to win the major national level tournaments like All India Sail Champion Colleges Nehru Hockey Tournament, All India Sail Champion Colleges Nehru Hockey Tournament and All India K. D. Babu Memorial Invitational Prize Money Hockey Tournament etc. along with the other Junior National tournaments.

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